

ADVERBS: DEFINITION, TYPES, USAGE AND EXAMPLES

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Abstract: In this scientific article, the subject of adverbs is widely covered, as well as brief information about adverbs and their types.

Keywords: definition, types, usage, example, property, provide, verb, speech, supermarket, prepositions, brave, luckily.

INTRODUCTION

Adverbs’ – What are they? How often are they used in sentences? Learn all about adverbs, its definition, types and usage. Take a look at the examples to have a complete understanding of the topic.

What Is an Adverb?

Like an adjective gives us more information about the noun in a sentence, an adverb is used to provide more information about the verb or the action in the sentence. It also has the property of describing the adjective or another adverb.

Definition of an Adverb

An adverb, according to the Oxford Learner’s Dictionary, is “a word that adds more information about place, time, manner, cause or degree to a verb, an adjective, a phrase or another adverb.” The Cambridge Dictionary defines an adverb as “a word that describes or gives more information about a verb, adjective, adverb, or phrase.”

Types of Adverbs

Adverbs are categorised into different types according to their functions when used in a sentence. Given below are the different types of adverbs.

- Adverbs of Manner
- Adverbs of Time
- Adverbs of Place
- Adverbs of Frequency
- Adverbs of Degree

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- Conjunctive Adverbs
- Examples of Adverbs

Now that you know what adverbs are and how there are different types of adverbs, let us look at some adverb examples to see how they can be used effectively in sentences.

How Adverbs are Used in Sentences

Unlike other parts of speech, adverbs can be placed at any part of the sentence (beginning, middle or end), and make complete sense without sounding absurd. Another characteristic is that multiple adverbs can be used in a sentence. Have a look at the following examples to have a clear understanding of the same.

I was planning to go to the supermarket to buy some groceries. However, I did not find the time to go. So I ordered online.

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Adverb Examples

An adverb can also modify adjectives, prepositions, and any other adverb. Even a whole sentence can be modified or adjusted using an adverb. This article briefly explains the adverb and also its types and usage. Let's go through the following cases.

“Rohit is a very brave person.”

Here ‘brave’ is an adjective that is used for ‘Rohit’ and ‘very’ is an adverb used to modify the adjective ‘brave’. By using the adverb ‘very’, it becomes more meaningful that Rohit is a much braver person. Let's see another case.

“She played very aggressively.”

Here ‘aggressively’ is an adverb used to modify the verb ‘played’ and ‘very’ is another adverb used to modify an adverb (aggressively) itself. Similarly, an adverb can also be used to modify a preposition. Let's understand through the following example.

“The aircraft flew exactly above the White House.”

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In this sentence, the preposition ‘above’ explains the relative position of the aircraft, and the adverb ‘exactly’ modifies the preposition by making it more emphasized. Let’s see one more use of an adverb.

“Luckily, She got selected for that job”

Hereby using the adverb ‘Luckily’ It becomes more apparent that She was lucky enough to get that job.

Conjunctive adverbs are often confused with coordinating conjunctions (e.g., “and,” “but”). However, unlike coordinating conjunctions, conjunctive adverbs can’t connect two clauses grammatically.

Instead, conjunctive adverbs are typically separated from a preceding clause by a period or semicolon and followed by a comma.

The car is damaged, besides it’s too expensive.

The car is damaged. Besides, it’s too expensive.

The car is damaged; besides, it’s too expensive.

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